

Dehydroxylation-Rehydration Studies on Kaolinite in Relation to Surface Area by Infrared Spectroscopy

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Infrared spectroscopy has been used by many authors to study the surface properties and reactivity of kaolinite minerals. Dehydroxylation involves elimination of structural OH groups with generation of metakaolin structure from kaolinite. Before further crystallisation stage, reconstitution may occur under certain conditions. In the present investigation dehydroxylated clay fractions were exposed to saturated humidity and reconstitution, if any, was studied by ir spectroscopy.

Results and Discussion

The six size fractions of kaolinite used in the present investigation and numbered as sample 1-6, varied widely in their surface area, i.e. from 3.1 to 19.2 m² g⁻¹. The ratio of SiO₂ to Al₂O₃, decreased with the increase in surface area, the maximum being 2.18 and the minimum 1.98. All the six size fractions exhibited characteristic endothermic and exothermic peaks in the temperature zones of 560-600 and 1020-1080° respectively. The cation exchange capacity increased with increase in surface area, the minimum value observed being 5.2 meq/100 g while the maximum 15.6 meq/100 g. This may be attributed to a greater degree of exposure of the edges and the corners (of the kaolinite mineral sample) which are generally the seats of charge-development through the 'broken bond' phenomenon in aqueous medium for kaolinite.

All the size fractions exhibited O-H stretching vibration in the region 3 400-3 700 cm⁻¹ except the sample with the lowest surface area. The latter might be due to the presence of the coarser particles which reduced both the reflectance and the band depth. Again greater molecular packing and atomic density for this fraction might have also played a role in the disappearance of the O-H. Stretching vibration creates stronger interaction of the polar OH groups with the large number of surrounding polar atoms or groups. Within a narrow range of surface area (8.4 to 12.6 μl² g⁻¹), there was an increasing trend of hydroxyl stretching vibration, which might well be correlated to the reduced influence of the surrounding environment on the hydroxyl stretching mode with decrease in atomic density (as the surface area increased). The sample with the largest surface area showed the least stretching vibration which might be due to the generation of higher surface charge through the broken bonds phenomenon. The surface charge created greater force of attraction or antisymmetric cou-

pling on the stretching vibration.

After dehydroxylation OH-stretching vibration disappeared from the spectrum of all the fractions indicating complete breakage of metal-hydroxyl bonds. When the dehydroxylated samples were equilibrated at saturation humidity all of them except sample no. 1, i.e. with the lowest surface area exhibited reconstitution of structural water. For the fraction having the largest surface area, the vibration was found to be shifted, towards the lower wave number region.

All the fractions showed the Si-O perpendicular band vibration at 1 032-1 038 cm⁻¹. This band appeared due to the distortion of the tetrahedral layer. These vibrations are associated with the development of strong dipole moment which produces electric field. Stretching of the Si-O bonds of these samples caused the thin plates of the layer silicate crystals to become electrically polarised like the dielectric in a parallel-plate condenser. The resulting field acted on the vibrating ions and with the increase in surface area the particle thickness decreased, causing the effect of such electric field to increase. So the Si-O stretching vibration increased with the increase in surface area.

On dehydration the frequency of particular vibration of such Si-O bond increased in each case. This might be due to greater intensity of electric charge produced in the dehydrated structure, which caused greater oscillation of the

TABLE I—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA BEFORE AND AFTER DEHYDROXYLATION AND ON REHYDRATION

	Sample no.	Surface area m ² /g	ν_{OH} cm ⁻¹	ν_{Si-O} cm ⁻¹
Before dehydroxylation	1	3.1	-	1 030
	2	5.4	3 536	1 032
	3	8.4	3 436	1 034
	4	9.6	3 492	1 036
	5	12.6	3 640	1 038
	6	19.2	3 430	1 042
After dehydroxylation	1	3.1	-	1 088
	2	5.4	-	1 084
	3	8.4	-	1 082
	4	9.6	-	1 078
	5	12.6	-	1 076
	6	19.2	-	1 070
After rehydration	1	3.1	-	1 042
	2	5.4	3 704	1 084
	3	8.4	3 488	1 074
	4	9.6	3 700	1 036
	5	12.6	3 700	1 034
	6	19.2	3 452	1 070

dipoles. Again the frequency of such vibration followed an inverse relationship with surface area which might be due to opposing effect of the neighbouring particles, on rehydration the frequency of such vibration followed an irregular order with surface area. The value decreased in each fraction compared to that in the dehydrated samples indicating a reduction in the surface charge intensity on rehydration due to agglomeration and reconstitution. Thus the complicated trend in these vibrational frequencies with surface area might be due to a delicate balance of two effects, namely, surface charge and the overlapping of the spheres of influence of the neighbouring particles.

Experimental

Rajmahal china clay (Bihar) was selected for the present investigation. The raw clay was purified from the associated impurities which mostly included non-clayey gritty matters, organic matters and soluble salts². The purified clay was properly ground and fractionated into six different size fractions through gravity sedimentation technique. Surface areas of the fractions were measured by Carle-Erba

Strumentazione instrument (Italy) which was based on gas adsorption BET principle. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Hitachi 270-30 spectrophotometer. The different size fractions were fired at 550° under equilibrium condition which is the dehydroxylation temperature of kaolinite. After dehydroxylation the samples were equilibrated at 100% relative humidity for rehydroxylation.

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